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Development of pH-sensitive films based on silk fibroin incorporated with anthocyanins extracted from red cabbage

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Intelligent food packaging has gained attention due to its potential to reduce food waste and enhance consumer safety. As expiration date labels are inaccurate, intelligent packaging, by monitoring changes in food or environmental conditions in real-time, can help consumers make informed decisions about food consumption and alert them of potential spoilage^[1,2]. This is particularly important for perishable food products like meat and seafood, which are highly sensitive to storage conditions and microbial contamination. Microbial growth on these products leads to a rapid degradation process and the formation of ammonium-based compounds. The amines produced cause an increase in the total volatile basic nitrogen concentration, resulting in a higher pH of the headspace above degrading food, which can serve as a clear indicator of food freshness^[3].

The objective of this study was to develop pH-sensitive films that have the potential to be used as a colorimetric indicator of meat freshness. The developed films were made from a silk fibroin aqueous solution containing anthocyanins extracted from red cabbage as sensing element. Silk fibroin is a protein extracted from silkworm cocoons. Owing to its biocompatibility, biodegradability, nontoxicity, and tunable mechanical properties, silk fibroin has a wide range of applications including edible food sensors^[4]. The developed films were evaluated for their color, optical and thermal properties and tested against real food samples. The color change of the films was compared to changes in UV-Vis absorption spectra and colony forming units (CFU) measured in the degrading food.

Keywords: intelligent packaging; pH indicators; silk fibroin; red cabbage.

References

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